

singular world perception, a world reinterpreted by other.

ILLUSTRATION AS A COMMUNICATION PROCESS

To comprehend conventional or artistic illustration's impact on children, we will first analyze the process of communication. Communication can be seen as the transmission of a message, by means of a code composed by signs. In this process there exists one transmitter and one receptor; the latter will assimilate the signs, decipher the code and receive the message.

If we adapt this process to our study and apply it to non-conventional illustrations: the sender composes his/her message by means of a code, passes his/her message to a receiver, through a familiar channel to children (illustration). But the combination of signs used by the illustrator can be to the receiver really difficult to interpret. If children find it difficult to decode the message conveyed by non-conventional illustration, we can conclude that the complexity of the creative representation might become something like noise inside the message.

"The concept of noise has been extended in a way that includes any kind of received signal that was not sent by the emitter; or anything that makes the intended signal more difficult to decode accurately. (...) The noise originated in either channel, public, sender or in the message itself, always confuses the intention of the issuer." (Fiske, 1990, p.22)

There are some authors who embrace more extreme perspectives, such as Nodelman (1988) or Kennedy (1979), who claims that: "it is now, beyond any tinge of doubt, simply wrong to assert that the recognition of pictures requires instruction in a convection of representation" (Kennedy, J., 1979. cit in Nodelman, P., 1988, p.6)

"The idea that pictures can clarify (...) implies that they put no particular stress on the mind, it assumes that they can operate in that way simply because they are more easily and more directly understood than words - that pictures can communicate automatically and be understood effortlessly by even very young children." (Nodelman, 1988, p.5)

These statements reflect the importance of a clear message and an immediate understanding of the meaning by the reader/child. There is always a risk that illustration may not be understood by children

because of its unusual plasticity or level of abstraction. It is extremely important to understand if the variety of non-conventional illustrations, available on the market, is adequate to the younger public.

Reflecting about this question, we aimed at gathering enough information about the non-conventional illustrations' impact on children (4 to 6 years old).

We also endeavor to disclose to illustrators and designers the children's perceptive process, so that the creation of children's books might benefit from it, and became a consistent combination between stimulating, creative, didactic factors to children, and the experimental, artistic work of the illustrators.

CHILDREN'S COGNITIVE PROCESS

To identify children's (from 4 to 6 years old) paradigms as far as the construction of concepts is concerned is crucial to this study. We aspire to understand the children's capacity to apprehend concepts, create memories, knowledge, and what factors interfere in this process: intelligence, genetics, education, external incentives. The whole mental game of capturing information, recognizing messages, assimilating concepts, interpreting visual or verbal texts, is developed in very different ways by children, teenagers and adults. Kosslyn (1980, 1984) referring to Gleitman states that:

"Children's thinking depends more on image than adults, because possibly their systems of verbal memory and conceptual are not sufficiently developed". (Gleitman, H., 1995, p.375). Furthermore Gleitman defends that to grasp the cognitive process of children we have to refer to Piaget: "the child's mind grows as his/her the body - what he/she knows, the way he/she is going to know, how he/she thinks about it and in the possibility of telling to others (sometimes in a endlessly way). This intellectual growth, from childhood to adulthood, it is commonly called cognitive development". (Gleitman, H., 1995, p.678) According to Piaget's theory, the group we have analyzed is included in the pre-operational stage, which encompasses children between 2 to 7 years old. This stage is divided into two other sub-phases:

Symbolic action phase / “make believe game” phase (2 to 4 years old) and the decentralization phase (4 to 7 years old), (Lewis, M., & Wolkmar, F., 1990). Children development phases are extremely important in their individual construction, but the phase under study, the decentralization phase, could be the one in which books and illustrations have more impact. This period between 4 to 7 years old is related to children’s integration in reality; when they actively assimilate the world around them (Dulamă, Ilovan and Vanea, 2009); enroll more intensely in social relationships (in pre-school and primary school); children begin to have a greater awareness of themselves and others.

“Accommodation to reality occurs in a gradually and increasing way, with a gradual “decentralization” of interests, perception and children’s points of view. “Decentralization” occurs because of the growing social involvement (...). Social interaction requires a virtual use of language and the revelation of what he/she thinks is not necessarily the same as their classmates think. Begins to see themselves and the world around them from different perspectives” (Lewis, M., & Wolkmar, F., 1993, p.36)

On the other hand, children’s play and fantasy concepts - their relation with toys and entertainment objects, like children’s books - occur in three different areas (Erikson, 1940): *macro-sphere - the real world where children interact; auto-sphere - internal fantasy life, which children construct parallel to reality; micro- sphere - toy’s world, “small, compact, manipulable and containable world”* (Lewis, M., & Wolkmar, F., 1993). Toys have the capacity to develop children’s minds; the act of playing with toys simulates life situations, creates scenarios and anticipates solutions for the future real life.

DISCLOSING THE RELATIONSHIP OF CHILDREN WITH ILLUSTRATION

Children’s books are extremely familiar to children, it’s something they usually interact with; they have the power to stimulate children’s knowledge and creativity, and represent a moment of discovery and exploration “the facts and relationships that children learn from their own explorations are more likely to be used and tend to be better retained than the materials that have only been sent to their

memory.” (Sprinthall, N. & Sprinthall, R., 1990, p.242).

So the idea that illustration plays an important role in children’s literature is almost a matter of consensus in the scientific community. Image and text exist side by side as synchronized languages to create one speech (Floch, 1991, cit in Panozzo, N., & Ramos, F., 2004). Illustration is children’s most familiar language and the easiest to grasp: “we saw that children readily recognize figures of various types - drawings, paints, photographs, moving pictures - as represent objects and events of the real world. Moreover, they know that these representations differ from real things” (Flavell, J., et al, 1999, p.69)

“Pictures speak louder than words”, illustrations have the capacity of conveying messages, even when the “reader” does not know how to read, like in our study group. In fact, children’s “reading” consists in visual image assimilation - colors, forms, contrasts - and oral text assimilation - grammatical games, melody, voice tone, contrasts, paralanguage.

Zohar Shavit (2003) defends that there are two text readers: one “pseudo-receiver” and one “real-receiver”: “we don’t expect that the child, which is the official reader of the text, do it entirely” (Shavit, 2003, cit in Campos, S., 2006, p.17).

We might say that children’s books, in contrast to other kinds of books, promote moments of sharing, interactivity, and have the ability to create a bond between individuals from different generations. Children’s books have also the ability to open fantastic new worlds, imagination, unreal things, fairy tales, etc. “The consequences of the entering fictional discourse in children literature are similar to those that occurred when Alice decided to cross the mirror and go to the other side: the reader is confronted with a universe which does not maintain a strict osmosis relationship with empirical, historical and factual world” (Sánchez Corral, 1999, cit in Campos, S., 2006, p.12).

These abilities make books extremely important in the construction of individual identity, and impart on how one will behave as an adult (Bettelheim, 1976). “If we are deprived of this natural resource [fantasy], our life becomes limited; without fantasies to give us hope, we do not have strength to face life’s adversities. Childhood is the time when these

fantasies need to be nourished.” (Bettelheim, B., 1976, p.156).

Carneiro and Manini (2007) have a study that explains exactly how the assimilation of illustrations occurs in children. This assimilation may occur in different stages “child passes through various stages in reading the work of art, and his/her interpretation of the images gets better with practice” (Parsons, 1992 cit in Carneiro, L., Manini, M., 2007). These stages are not related to children ages, but to the frequency with which they interact with books - more interaction with books corresponds to more advanced stages. The first stage has the name of “firstness” - it consists in the assimilation of main features such as colors, “pure qualities”, in ignoring details and the relation between elements: “There is not a concern if the image is abstract or figurative since it has bright, clear and abundant colors” (Carneiro, L., & Manini, M., 2007).

In the next stage, “secondness”, children have the ability to assimilate the theme behind the illustrations and the relationship between elements, “analytical and comparative relations” (Carneiro, L., & Manini, M., 2007), realism it’s overestimated, “conception of beauty, in this stage is connected to proximity to the realism displayed in the image” (Carneiro, L., & Manini, M., 2007).

In “thirdness” stage, children can relate illustrations and theme to their personal experience, can create new situations, and draw conclusions.

Carneiro (2007) and Manini (2007) have raised an interesting question, “what instruments can the illustrator use to stimulate children to get to the “thirdness” stage? The same authors answered that illustrators can use colors, “wire, scene elements, dialogs boxes, character’s physical features, all to increase the expressiveness of the image and promotes the reader to discover new meanings that arise from the image reading and interpretation process” (Carneiro, L., & Manini, M., 2007). These instruments are related to the illustrator’s practice, but other instruments are worth mentioning, such as: psychology; cognitive development and direct interaction with children to understand their needs; children’s illustration semiological knowledge; socio and cultural information about our study public.

THE RESEARCH - THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND EXPERIMENTS OUTCOMES

To create a strong link between the illustrator’s work and the awareness of children’s needs in different ages (knowledge, creative motivation, and cognitive development) will improve the conception of more adequate and functional books.

Common sense allows us to identify, in a general way, which are the most adequate books for children, which have the most interesting or basic illustrations. But this empirical analysis has no scientific basis to support it. Therefore, it is very important to create a theoretical framework in which we can evaluate books and illustrations typology.

The categorization of illustrations was supported by Massironi’s work (1982) in which he ‘dismantles’ the illustration’s mechanism making an analysis of the representation process. This analysis comprehends graphic characteristics he calls ‘primary elements’, linked with the illustrator, the way he/she organizes the representation system (line, plan, addition, exclusion) and also the ‘secondary elements’ that concern context (place, time, culture, illustrator personality).

To Massironi (1982) the illustrator’s goal is to create an “illusion”: “The concrete representation systems are therefore, fine and excogitate performances to construct illusions (...) to the illustrators the illusion is the end to attain, is the way to construct situations in line with what is supposed to be seen by the observer” (Massironi, M., 1982, p.20).

Massironi claims that the final product is an illusion since all representation, even the most realistic, will be always unreal, “facilitate the evocation of a compelling image despite the fact that not even one of the strokes matches with what we call reality”. (Massironi, M., 1982, p.20). The author also states that the construction of illusion should be understood/decoded “inside the exact limit” (Massironi, M., 1982), if we define this “exact limit” we can determinate whether an illustration is adequate for children.

All these concepts were summarized in the figure 1, (author’s scheme).

Massironi’s primary elements were incorporated in our Framework. Designated as illustration’s internal dimension, they are decisive to the final outcomes.

Figure 1. Research's scheme summarizing Massironi's theory.

The external dimension of our framework is concerned with the relationship between image and text: it concerns the story's theme; the way elements are added, subtracted or emphasized, focusing on the literal or connotative character of the illustration in its relationship with the text (figure 2).

The schemes 3 and 4 (figures 3 and 4) show to us the descriptions of artistic illustrations and conventional illustrations.

The framework conveys an external description of the way perception and representation occurs in children. The way children perceive illustration was analyzed through the critical assessment of their reactions to chosen books (from both categories) that were presented to twenty children in several (videotaped) sessions made in the school

environment; later on, the children were asked to draw several aspects of the story. Moreover, children's drawings were also significant data for our investigation. The elements added or subtracted in the children's drawings, in comparison to the original illustrations, as well as the elements' scale, colors, etc, are extremely relevant to understand how the story influenced each child.

The drawing issue was addressed having as its main reference Rudolph Arnheim's work, bearing in mind the aspects of children's psychological development according to the different age stages as proposed by Piaget. Children's drawings were analyzed according to different parameters that made it possible to assess the way the story was assimilated and how it stimulated children.

Figure 2. Research's framework incorporating Massironi's primary elements.

Our main goal is to determine whether children remained faithful to the conventional representation elements or made the option to perform more creatively. The term “conventional” can be associated to erroneous interpretations, and as such it is important to make clear that in this study we use the term “conventional” when referring to

drawings that satisfy the criteria described by Rudolf Arhneim (1954).

Children's representation can be divided into several development stages: use of circle for all representation; “differentiation”, that consists in the use of circles and angular geometry; and the elements fusion (element’s addition or subdivision).

Figure 3. Descriptive framework of artistic illustrations.

“When a child self-portrayed with a simple pattern of circles, ovals and straight lines, he/she does so this not because that is what she/he sees when looks

in the mirror, not because he/she is unable to produce a more accurate portrayal, but because simple sketch congregates all the conditions of what

Figure 4. Descriptive framework of conventional illustrations.

a child expects in a picture” (Rudolf, A.,1954, p.158).

In order to achieve more exact conclusions, it should be constructive to analyze the compilation of

children’s drawings before the experiment. This way we have a history of the drawings’ evolution, to better contextualize the drawings after the experiment.

In our study it was not possible to put that procedure into practice, so, in order to assess the impact of both categories in children, a second experiment was carried out after one month, in which they had to draw some of the characters of the stories they saw previously.

The perception issue was also considered in view of Arnheim's work, who regards perception as linked to psychological questions, which makes it much more difficult to arrive at conclusions: "All perception is also thinking, all reasoning is also intuition, all observation is also invention" (Arnheim, R., 1954, p.5).

It would have been interesting to make use of

Figure 5. Children's group that participate in survey.

Figure 6. Example of a child's illustration, after the presentation of a conventional book.

Figure 7. Example of a child's illustration, after the presentation of an artistic book.

Neuroscience technologies to evaluate the perception information in this kind of study. So, the present Framework can be summarized by describing the four steps in the proposed analysis:

- *Image* - detailed characterization of the illustration: colors, plans, type of lines, added and subtracted elements;
- *Reading moment* - children's comments, levels of concentration and participation; paralinguage;
- *Representation of the story by children* - choice of the story characters or scenes to be drawn; added and subtracted elements (in relation to the original image); color, contour/spot; special characteristics.
- *Drawing the characters in the story (1 month later)* - common elements to the previously drawn, conventional and non-conventional elements.

Other agendas can be analyzed with a more thorough and extensive study, like assimilated concepts our new information by children. The agendas exposed in this study were the more immediately outline.

EXPERIMENTS CONCLUSIONS

Our qualitative study made use of some quantitative data treatment (classify, disclose situations), nevertheless it is important to reiterate that this study is, in fact, qualitative, and that our study criteria are extremely subjective. Our results are not so much conclusive as interpretative. So, the outcome of these experiments made it possible to arrive at some conclusions. First, that those children were more impressed by books that have non-conventional illustrations. That was made clear by their strong and immediate reaction to those books, expressing their surprise and commenting in a rich way the contact they had with that type of illustration. Conversely, the conventional illustrations, despite being less enthusiastically commented on, were the ones best assimilated, since their elements were reproduced in the representation session one month later; however, the same did not happen with non-conventional illustrations. In addition, it was observable that the use of one isolated non-conventional element in a context of conventional illustration made the children keep in mind this particular element

drawing it on the two occasions (first contact and one month later). Furthermore, it was noticeable that conventional illustration compelled children to add extra creative elements to the existing ones when drawing what they had seen. That did not occur with non-conventional illustrations, in which children added substantially fewer extra elements. Considering these observations it seems that the contact with conventional illustrations stimulates children to a greater degree regarding the representation, being a possible reason why children found those images too familiar and simple and therefore attempted to enrich them.

HOW USEFUL CAN BE THIS NEW INFORMATION?

This study gave us the opportunity to design a conceptual tool that allows everyone to understand beforehand some of the most important effects a book will make on a child as regards perception and representation ways. This framework can be used as a complement tool to “children’s books market-surveys”, to understand how the information will be assimilated by children. Therefore, the study must be considered as a tool to illustrators in order to approach their practice under a different perspective that presupposes the critical questioning of how his/her message should be structured and what possible impact it will have on children, namely in what concerns the enhancement of the child’s creativity and aesthetic sense.

PAPER’S CONTRIBUTION TO THE SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY, SPECIFICALLY IN COMMUNICATION DESIGN

This investigation is not intended to achieve a single and irrefutable conclusion, but to expose, with accuracy and detail, a particular instance of how children perceive and represent. We recommend this study as a basis for other researches in this study area, complementing it with more experiences. On a pedagogical level such a study could help pre-school teachers and even parents in making a better selection of books, based on aspects like creativity, memorization or stimulus.

An analysis of these questions will contribute to the knowledge increase in areas like illustration, children literature, semiology, in scientific community included in Communication Design.

WHAT HAS BEEN DONE LATELY ABOUT THIS SUBJECT

Several studies and researches were made about children’s books, illustrations and their impact on children. In our study we address some authors such as Camargo (2008), who focus on the relationship between image and text; the authors Carneiro and Manini (2007), regarding the different children perception stages in reading a children’s book; Silva (2005), Pereira (2006) and Campos (2006), who address several themes related to children’s literature and the relationship between text and image.

Another kind of researches focuses more on children’s perception, using as a tool of study children’s drawing. Researchers like Eristi and Kurt (2011), Moore (1987) or Rennie and Jarvis (1995) about technology perception; Barraza (1999), King (1995) and Matthews (1985) about environment perception; Dulamã, Ilovan and Vanea (2009) about the relationship between children’s drawings and the environment they live in; Belet and Türkkan (2007) about children’s perception of European Union; Yurtal and Artut (2007) focusing on perception of violence; Belet and Eristi (2010), about cultural perception.

In a word, the purpose of this investigation is to sensitize authors and artists to the specific target of children’s books, i.e. young readers, so as to promote their growth as individuals with a sense of aesthetics. Thus we mean to contribute to the development of Communication Design, in such a way as to provide illustration projects inserted in this area with a stronger and more accurate knowledge of their target consumers.

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